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EVALUATION METHODOLOGY OF INFORMATION SECURITY OF IT SYSTEMS BASED ON FUZZY RULES

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Abstract

There is a growing tendency to incorporate biometric elements into complex technical systems designed by humans in order to imitate natural systems. This trend is especially evident in the field of information technology, where artificial neural networks come to the fore. The topological structure of neural networks is similar to the structure of the nervous system in biological systems, as well as the architecture of modern IT systems, such as corporate telecommunications networks.

Using fuzzy input vectors, the structural and parametric adjustment of the neuro-fuzzy classifier block for the adaptive security mechanism is carried out through a control algorithm that trains neuro-fuzzy networks using fuzzy connection mechanisms.

Keywords: information security, IT systems, biometric.

Introduction

The hierarchical organization of information security systems shares similarities with biological systems in nature. The similarity between biological systems and IT security systems lies in their hierarchical structure, which includes knowledge gathering mechanisms in immune defense information platforms and neural networks. Known for its crucial role in the evolution of living organisms, the nervous system serves as an adaptive tool for interaction with the environment. It is believed that the human nervous system is responsible for the formation of basic reflexes that respond to external stimuli and facilitate self-organization within the biosystem. These reflexes, stored in genetic memory, are transmitted to subsequent generations at a lower level of information security.

Self-organizing behavior plays an important role in ensuring purposeful actions within a biosystem. It necessitates an educational system and gives rise to a new form of memory in the form of an adaptive information platform in neural networks. The transition to a qualitatively developed nervous system is determined by behavioral responses within biosystems. The presence of such responses confirms the complex relationship between external influences and body reactions. Various natural mechanisms facilitate the transmission of information between DNA and nerve cells. Behavioral information is formed on the basis of genetically transmitted behavioral responses fixed in the information platform of the nervous system. However, biosystem responses go beyond hereditary responses and include the accumulation of life experiences that are passed on to future generations through education. The results of this education become rooted in the DNA and serve as a means of transmitting knowledge to subsequent generations [1-4].

The creation of intelligent information security systems is based on the hierarchical organization of information protection, i.e.:

- similarity of IT system architecture with biological system architecture;

- a number of known mechanisms of information security in biosystems listed below:

1. Hierarchy of conservation levels in the biosphere, nucleotide-codon-gene-chromosome-DNA-...-organism-...-biosphere.

2. Storage of genetic information at the lower levels of the hierarchy (codon-gene-chromosome-DNA), encoding and decoding of information, mechanisms of chromosomal mutations, information distribution based on the "self/other" criterion.

3. At higher levels of the hierarchy, sense organs (for example, receptors) are used to organize the connection between the external environment and the biosystem, and experience is gathered in the neural network structures of the nervous system.

4. The content of information is not related to changes in life experience, and the change of genetic information is not related to the change of the form of representation.

5. Biosystems are capable of adapting to the process of information security, while accepting life experience that allows success in important situations, including recognizing the behavior of others and themselves in a constantly changing and complex environment.

- Existence of hierarchy of information security levels in IT systems:

1. Within adaptive information security systems, important information is stored in two hierarchical levels in information fields: the lower level, which serves as a platform for threat identification, and the upper level, which acts as a platform of accumulated experience, where protection mechanisms against known information threats are defined.

2. The level of inviolability located at the lower level of adaptive information security systems is aimed at checking message compatibility in the IT system and ensuring the reliability of information presentation formats (containers) using the "self/external" criterion.

3. Identification of information within information security systems is unique to each system and is usually associated with format rather than content.

4. The receptor level located at the upper level of the information security system plays a decisive role in facilitating interactive interaction with the environment and gathering heuristic knowledge through the information platform in adaptive information security systems.

5. Information transfer and inheritance in adaptive information security systems involves the transfer of information platforms from the immune and receptor levels of biosystems to subsequent generations formed during the life cycle of a specific IT system and creates conditions for the effective implementation of the system.

1. The structure of the hierarchical adaptive information security system model

The basis of this model for adaptive information security in corporate telecommunication networks is the methodology for assessing the level of protection and its effectiveness. To achieve this, various adaptive information security tools should be used [2,5]. These tools include artificial multilayer feedforward neural networks, fuzzy logic inference systems integrated into the logic base of multilayer neural networks, and traditional systems of fuzzy implication rules. The purpose of using these tools is to ensure effective coordination within the adaptive information security system.

In addition, the model should include a structured approach to the overall information security system, which involves defining clear procedures and guidelines. It should also incorporate specialized software and tools that can assess security performance against information threats. In addition, a rating system should be created specifically to assess the security level of the corporate telecommunications network itself.

By combining these elements, an adaptive information security system model can effectively address the challenges and complexities associated with ensuring robust security in corporate telecommunications networks.

The nature of information threats is constantly changing and highlights the critical need for adaptation in the protection mechanisms used in open corporate networks. Another important aspect of the designed information security system is the ability to use the accumulated heuristic knowledge about potential information threats. This knowledge is obtained from the relevant information domain component within the multi-level hierarchy of protection mechanisms.

However, it is important to note that it is not possible or practical to include a wide range of different security mechanisms in an informatization object. In practice, corporate networks usually use only the minimum defense mechanisms necessary to effectively deal with potential threats identified during the design of the information security system. By carefully selecting and applying the appropriate composition of protection mechanisms, an information security system can create a balance between adaptability and efficiency, providing optimal protection against potential information threats in corporate networks [3,5-7].

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By carefully selecting and applying the appropriate composition of protection mechanisms, an information security system can strike a balance between adaptability and efficiency, providing optimal protection against potential information threats in corporate networks [6].

Fuzzy rule-based systems in the form of fuzzy neural networks are used to achieve further adaptation and analysis in the information security system. These networks are trained using input vectors whose components are represented as fuzzy sets that describe the characteristics of information attacks. Neural network classifiers are trained to generate clusters that match implication rules in a fuzzy inference system.

Hybrid classifiers combining neural networks and fuzzy inference systems are trained in a similar way, but use predefined vectors of known information threats. This allows effective classification and recognition of potential threats within the framework of adaptive information security mechanisms. In addition, the assessment of information security indicators and the overall rating of the corporate network are calculated based on preliminary expert assessments. These indicators play a decisive role in the general methodology of assessing the security of the corporate network. They are used to analyze and optimize the structural and parametric aspects of expert evaluation arrays, neural network classifiers, and fuzzy rule-based systems. By incorporating these methods, the information security system can continuously improve its performance, adapt to changing threats, and optimize assessment processes to increase the overall security of the corporate network.

Analogous to systems simulating nature, in an adaptive information security system, theoretical information is stored and can be transmitted from generation to generation through the replication and subsequent transformation of the corporate network in the form of distributed adaptive information fields of neural networks:

- areas of known potential threats of defense mechanism ("immune") levels of resistance to threats;
- areas of interactive knowledge obtained at receptor levels of information security.

The process of matching "immune" defense levels dealing with known potential threat areas is closely re-

lated to grouping and classification tasks. These positions are responsible for expanding the information scope of known threats at lower levels of the information protection system hierarchy. Any changes or updates to previously identified data threats must be entered into the heuristic knowledge space at higher levels of the protection system hierarchy. To achieve this, a specialized topological structure based on a system of fuzzy implication rules implemented within the logical framework of a multilayer neural network is used.

The process of adapting the system of fuzzy implication rules involves adjusting the parameters of the fuzzy neural network using a supervised learning algorithm. This algorithm allows adapting the system of fuzzy implication rules by matching information protection mechanisms with known information threats. By continuously updating and improving fuzzy implication rules, the system becomes more adept at effectively responding to and neutralizing potential threats.

Through this adaptive process, the information security system evolves and improves its ability to address emerging challenges and new variants of known threats. A supervised learning algorithm ensures that the system remains up-to-date and capable of accurately classifying and mitigating information security risks.

2. Mechanisms of building the model of the adaptive information security system

To ensure the intelligent and adaptive capabilities of the information security system, it is very important to choose tools that can store the acquired knowledge and create a distributed information space within a neural network with fuzzy properties.

Fuzzy logical inference plays an important role in the concept of an adaptive information security system. It involves a fuzzy representation of the input data to the neural network, which allows the incorporation of heuristic knowledge provided by information security experts. This idea is implemented through the development and optimization of a system of fuzzy implication rules integrated into the logical framework of a neural network. By integrating a system of fuzzy implication rules into the hierarchical structure of an information

security system and training it using known threat data, it is possible to eliminate inconsistencies within the rules, improve the existing system, and synthesize new rules through the analysis of fuzzy rules. An additional aspect in building a model for an adaptive information security system is the ability of neural networks and hybrid neuro-fuzzy systems to classify and group information attacks and potential threats. These systems are equipped to perform classification and clustering tasks that help identify and organize various information security threats. Collectively, the implementation of these features contributes to the adaptability, intelligence and effectiveness of the information security system, allowing it to effectively respond to evolving threats and ensure the protection of critical information assets [3-5].

Neural network logic-based fuzzy inference mechanism. Fuzzy logic inference is a component of fuzzy neural networks that use fuzzy inference systems learned from previous experience. These systems are usually built by combining regular neural networks with a fuzzy rule system. The mechanism of drawing conclusions from fuzzy logic is built by information security specialists in the form of implicative rules, for example:

$$\begin{aligned}
 R_1 &: \text{“ If } x = A_1, \text{ Then } y = B_1 \text{”}; \\
 R_2 &: \text{“ If } x = A_2, \text{ Then } y = B_2 \text{”}; \\
 &\dots \\
 R_n &: \text{“ If } x = A_n, \text{ Then } y = B_n \text{”}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

In this case, x is the input linguistic variable (e.g. threat) and y is the output linguistic variable (e.g. defense mechanisms). A_i and B_i ($i=1 \div n$) are the corresponding linguistic variables.

The rules of implication of the form $R=A \Rightarrow B$ used in the system (fuzzy relations) show the security expert's knowledge in the form of cause-and-effect relations between the protection mechanism and the results related to the selection of threats. The symbol “ \Rightarrow ” used here represents the fuzzy implication operation. In general, it is observed that different types of effects are used in the fuzzy environment. Below, table 1 shows the most common types [8].

Table 1

Fuzzy implication operators		
№	The name of the implication	Fuzzy implication operators
1.	L. Zadeh	$I_m(x, y) = \max(1 - x, \min(x, y))$
2.	Yager	$I_E(x, y) = y^x$
3.	Lukasiewicz	$I_a(x, y) = \min(1, 1 - x + y)$
4.	Kleene – Dienes	$I_b(x, y) = \max(1 - x, y)$
5.	Minimum (Mamdani)	$I_c(x, y) = \min(x, y)$
6.	Gaines	$I_{\Delta}(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1, & x \leq y \\ \frac{y}{x}, & x > y \end{cases}$
7.	Standard Star (Godel)	$I_g(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1, & x \leq y \\ y, & x > y \end{cases}$

A relation R can be directly called a fuzzy subset of the $X \times Y$ Cartesian product. Here, X is the complete set of information threats and Y is the defense mechanism. The process of obtaining a fuzzy output based on

the entity and existing knowledge can be represented as the following composition rule:

$$B = A \circ R = A \circ (A \Rightarrow B),$$

where the sign " ° " means any operation (example max-min):

$$\mu_{\tilde{G}}(i) = \max_{w \in W} (\min(\mu_{\tilde{A}}(w), \mu_{\tilde{D}}(w, i))).$$

Fuzzy logical inference mechanism involves sequential execution of the following procedures [7, 8]:

1. Application of fuzziness, that is, fuzzification or, to put it more simply, determining the degree of accuracy for each information threat for each specific rule, based on the given membership functions of the fuzzy subsets of the field of input parameters described by suitable conditions;

2. Logical inference, which involves forming a fuzzy inference based on the degree of truth of threats for each rule, forming a fuzzy subset for each defense mechanism;

3. Composition of rules: the fuzzy subsets of the universal set for each defense mechanism obtained in the previous step are combined according to all rules in order to create a fuzzy subset for the set of all defense mechanisms;

4. Defuzzification, which shows the numerical representation of the fuzzy results obtained in the previous step. In this step, the collection of fuzzy results for all rules is transformed into a numerical value of the overall security level of the corporate network.

Fuzzy logic inference procedures can be implemented using MATLAB's fuzzy inference system notation, as exemplified by the following set of implication rules illustrated in Figure 1.

$$\begin{aligned} R_1 &: \text{"If } x = A, \text{ Then } y = D \text{"}; \\ R_2 &: \text{"If } x = B, \text{ Then } y = E \text{"}; \\ R_3 &: \text{"If } x = C, \text{ Then } y = F \text{"}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

In this scenario, the variables x, y, and z represent input linguistic variables related to known threats, and y represents an output linguistic variable related to the overall security of the corporate network. Fuzzy sets A, B, C, D, E and F are used to describe the semantic information of information threat characteristics.

Figure 1. Application of rules (2) in MATLAB/Fuzzy inference system

The procedures of the fuzzy inference mechanism are explained in the following section [9, 10]:

Step 1: Based on the values of the variables according to the semantics of A, B, and C, the accuracy rates of each of the information threats $\alpha(x_0)=A(x_0)$, $\alpha(y_0)=B(y_0)$ and $\alpha(z_0)=C(z_0)$ are non-defined for fuzzy implication rules.

Step 2: using the logical operation "min" according to the degrees of truth $\alpha(x_0)=A(x_0)$, $\alpha(y_0)=B(y_0)$ and $\alpha(z_0)=C(z_0)$, the above semantics of D, E and F parts are extracted, after which fuzzy results are formed for each of the rules that are a fuzzy subset of the universal set for each protection mechanism.

Step 3: Using the logic operation "max", the truncated semantics are combined and a network of connected fuzzy subsets is formed, described by the semantics of $\mu_{\tilde{A}}(y)$ and corresponding to the fuzzy logic output for the output variable w of the corporate's total protection level.

Step 4: The numerical value of the extracted linguistic variable term is determined using, for example, the defuzzification centering method.

3. Fuzzy classification of information properties

A combination of neural networks and fuzzy logic elements is a suitable approach for classification mechanism within adaptive information security tools. Neural networks offer the advantage of training capabilities, while fuzzy logic systems provide transparency in the interpretation of fuzzy results to solve information security problems. By using a hybrid neuro-fuzzy system that combines these techniques, the benefits of both neural network structures and fuzzy logic systems can be used to leverage the heuristic knowledge of information security professionals.

As can be seen in Table 2, the development of hybrid neuro-fuzzy systems demonstrates their effectiveness in classifying information threats. One type of hybrid neuro-fuzzy system focuses on defining a crisp class for an input vector, while other variations are used to construct fuzzy systems based on a set of fuzzy implication rules. The method of constructing a neuro-fuzzy classifier using a fuzzy logic inference mechanism can be used to classify adaptive information security mechanisms. It involves using a neural network with fuzzy synaptic weights to process fuzzy feature vectors of information threats.

Table 2

Neural networks used to solve the classification problem

A type of fuzzy neural network	Weights	Introduction	Any output
1	fluent	Fuzzy	fluent
2	fluent	Fuzzy	Fuzzy
3	Fuzzy	Fuzzy	Fuzzy
4	Fuzzy	fluent	Fuzzy
5	fluent	fluent	Fuzzy
6	Fuzzy	fluent	fluent
7	Fuzzy	Fuzzy	fluent

The fuzzy logic inference mechanism is based on the heuristic knowledge of information security experts and takes the form of a system of fuzzy implication rules, exemplified by the following type:

$$\begin{aligned}
 R_1 &: \text{“ If } x_1 = \tilde{A}_{11} \text{ and } x_2 = \tilde{A}_{12} \text{ and .. and } x_n = \tilde{A}_{1n} \text{ Then } y = \tilde{B}_1 \text{”}; \\
 R_2 &: \text{“ If } x_1 = \tilde{A}_{21} \text{ and } x_2 = \tilde{A}_{22} \text{ and .. and } x_n = \tilde{A}_{2n} \text{ Then } y = \tilde{B}_2 \text{”}; \\
 &\dots \\
 R_m &: \text{“ If } x_m = \tilde{A}_{m1} \text{ and } x_2 = \tilde{A}_{m2} \text{ and .. and } x_n = \tilde{A}_{mn} \text{ Then } y = \tilde{B}_m \text{”};
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3}$$

Here, x_i and y_j ($i=1 \div n; j=1 \div m$) are fuzzy input and output variables, respectively, for defense mechanisms and information threats; and \tilde{B} denotes the fuzzy sets that express the conditions corresponding to them.

Now suppose that the complete space of hazards (premises) is given by $X=\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ and the complete space of protection mechanisms (outcomes) is given by $Y=\{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_m\}$. Then there is a fuzzy causal relationship between x_i and y_j ($i=1 \div n; j=1 \div m$) in the form $x_i \Rightarrow y_j$, which $R=[r_{ij}]$ ($i=1 \div n; j=1 \div m$) can be presented in the form of a matrix. The bases and consequences can be represented as fuzzy sets (\tilde{A} and \tilde{B}) in the X and Y spaces, their relations can be given in the following form: $\tilde{B} = A \circ R$, where the sign " \circ " is the logical operation of rule composition, i.e., denoting the maximum composition is a logical operator.

To implement a system of fuzzy implication rules in adaptive information security tools based on fuzzy feature vectors of threats, the neuro-fuzzy classifier should perform the following actions [1, 3]:

- Fuzzification based on given membership functions for fuzzy sets included in the domain of definition. As a result of fuzzification, a degree of truth is determined for each potential threat according to the duration of the fuzzy variable.
- Logical inference involves creating a fuzzy conclusion for each of the implication rules based on the degree of truth of potential information threats. This result is a fuzzy subset of the universe for each output linguistic variable associated with the corresponding protection mechanism.
- The composition stage involves combining the fuzzy subsets obtained in the previous stage for each output linguistic variable by all rules to form a single fuzzy subset of the universe of discourse for all output variables.

The maximum number of input vectors with fuzzy components in the full space of information threats described by the N-dimensional feature vector $X=\{x_1, x_2,$

$\dots, x_n\}$ is given by all possible combinations of coordinates x_i . Each input vector from the X-space can be associated with a fuzzy neuron of a hybrid neuro-fuzzy classifier that performs a logical inference operation such as "min" logical operation [7-9]. The extrapolation of the results of the fuzzy logic inference to the full space of fuzzy outputs is achieved by the operation of rule composition, so that each output vector from the space Y can be associated with a fuzzy artificial neuron of the neuro-fuzzy classifier, which, for example, performs the logical operation "max".

A neuro-fuzzy classifier for n-dimensional normalized hazard vectors X with fuzzy coordinates (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) can be represented as a three-layer fuzzy neural network (figure 2), where:

- In the first layer, there are n fuzzy artificial neurons with complementary fuzzy connections and form n pairs of fuzzy expressions of the form: $x_i = S$ and $x_i = L$ ($i=1 \div n$), where the coordinates in the input vector of n threats is the number.
 - The hidden layer consists of up to $2n$ fuzzy neurons, each of which performs a logical inference operation (for example, "min") on the combinations of fuzzy sets of the 1st layer of the neural network, producing fuzzy results for the classification of information threats forms the system.
 - The output layer consists of m fuzzy neurons and is equal to the number of coordinates in the output vector. These neurons simulate a fuzzy composition operation (max) on the classifier outputs of layer 2 of the neural network to generate m-dimensional Y vectors of fuzzy outputs (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_m).
- Fuzzy neurons from the first layer generate complementary pairs of truth values for input fuzzy variables x_i representing the coordinates of the input vector X of threats [10]. For a given value of the X coordinate of the threat vector in the interval of the determination area, the value of the ordinate of the S (small) and L (large) membership functions is assigned to each value of the fuzzy variable, and this value can be up to 1.

Figure 2. Neuro-fuzzy classifier and membership functions of complementary fuzzy transitions

The pair of membership functions S and L depicted in Figure 2 form two fuzzy relations that form one complementary fuzzy relation.

If the second layer of a fuzzy multilayer neural network consists of the maximum number of fuzzy neurons performing the logical AND operation, the intermediate vector of fuzzy results must include all potential fuzzy results related to the classification of features of possible hazard vectors.

The third layer of the fuzzy multilayer neural network includes fuzzy neurons that perform the logical OR operation. The number of these neurons corresponds to the fuzzy results of type y_j ($j=1 \div m$) and reflects the heuristic knowledge controlled by the expert. This layer generates a vector of fuzzy outputs based on a system of implication rules.

Conclusion

Using fuzzy threat vectors, further structural and parametric adjustment of the neuro-fuzzy classifier for the adaptive security mechanism is carried out through a control algorithm that trains neuro-fuzzy networks using fuzzy connection mechanisms.

Through structural and parametric tuning of the neuro-fuzzy classifier with a training set of known hazard vectors, it is possible to identify potential logical inconsistencies and correct non-causal relationships (or generation) within the system of fuzzy implication rules.

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